

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Grain grades in relation to seedling growth and productivity

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This study was designed to determine the relationship of 1,000-grain weight to seedling growth and productivity.

Spikelets of IET75737, IET7574, and IET7575 were sorted by immersing them in 1.0, 1.06, and 1.18 specific gravity solutions using 0, 90, and 270 g common salt/liter of water. Floating grains were categorized as partially filled, average, good, and very good. The graded grains were tested for germination and seedling growth in the nursery and for yield potential in the field.

Germination and seedling growth, influenced by seed size up to 10 d, compensated at 20-22 d after sowing (Table 1). As a result, crop productivity was not affected (Table 2).

Table 1. Germination and seedling growth in relation to grain grade. ^a Andhra Pradesh, India.

Grain grade	Germination (%)						Seedling growth (cm)					
	IET7573		IET7574		IET7575		IET7573		IET7574		IET7575	
	10 DAS	20 DAS	10 DAS	20 DAS	10 DAS	20 DAS	10 DAS	22 DAS	10 DAS	22 DAS	10 DAS	22 DAS
Partially filled	36	91	15	84	17	89	8.0	17.4	8.6	14.8	9.7	19.7
Average	59	93	21	85	31	89	8.5	17.4	8.7	14.8	10.2	19.7
Good	68	94	30	86	45	89	9.6	17.5	8.9	14.7	10.8	19.4
Very good	95	95	48	88	57	90	9.8	17.4	9.2	14.8	11.3	19.5

^a Av of 3 replications. DAS = days after sowing.

Table 2. Yield in relation to grain grade. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Grain grade	Yield (t/ha)		
	IET7573	IET7574	IET7575
Partially filled	3.6	3.8	3.8
Average	3.4	4.0	3.8
Good	3.7	4.4	4.0
Very good	3.7	4.1	4.0
CD (0.05)	V = NS T = NS V in T = NS T in V = NS		V = 11.7% T = 10.6%

Because consumer preference is mainly for size and shape of the whole kernel, fully filled grain may be used

for consumption, rather than for seed. □

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DISEASE RESISTANCE

Susceptibility of rice hybrids to blast (BI)

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We studied the susceptibility of six F₁ hybrids to BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara during navarai (Dec-Jan to Mar-Apr 1983-84). TKM9 was the base parent, crossed with Co 29 (resistant), IR36 (moderately resistant), and IR50 (highly susceptible). The Uniform Blast

Susceptibility of rice hybrids to BI. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cross	BI	Disease intensity ^a			Heterosis ^b (%)
		F ₁ hybrid (av)	Ovule parent (av)	Pollen parent (av)	
TKM9/Co 29	Leaf	5.4	4.8	2.6	45.95**
	Neck	2.5	3.3	1.2	11.11
Co 29/TKM9	Leaf	4.2	2.6	4.8	13.51
	Neck	2.5	1.2	3.4	8.70
TKM9/IR36	Leaf	4.4	4.8	3.6	4.76
	Neck	2.3	3.3	1.5	-4.17
IR36/TKM9	Leaf	3.8	3.6	4.8	-9.52
	Neck	2.1	1.5	3.3	-12.50
TKM9/IR50	Leaf	4.6	4.8	6.6	-19.30*
	Neck	1.3	3.3	5.2	-69.41**
IR50/TKM9	Leaf	3.4	6.6	4.8	-40.35**
	Neck	0.3	5.2	3.3	-92.94**

^a By SES. ^b Significant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Nursery (UBN) screening technique was used and disease rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*.

Scores indicated the dominance of

susceptibility over resistance (see table). The high heterosis for leaf and neck Bl resistance in TKM9/IR50 and its reciprocal shows that these two parents may have complementary

genes although they are individually susceptible. TKM9/Co 29 and its reciprocal were susceptible to both leaf and neck Bl. □

Tolerance of Sitopas crosses for ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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Sitopas, an Indonesian variety, has been reported as susceptible to but tolerant of RSV. Crosses were made to transfer its resistance to IR varieties and lines.

We evaluated 523 F₃ lines from 5 crosses of Sitopas and 3 IR varieties and lines: IR20, susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) and intolerant of RSV; IR8234-OT-9-2, resistant to BPH biotype 1 but intolerant of RSV; and sitopas, tolerant of RSV but susceptible to BPH biotype 1.

Seeds were soaked in petri dishes in five batches mid-Jun to late Aug. Germinating seeds were transplanted in clay pots. Seedlings were artificially inoculated with RSV at 11 d by the standard mass screening method in the greenhouse. Seedlings infected with RSV were transplanted in the field at 45 d from early Aug to early Oct.

Reaction of rice varieties and Sitopas progenies to RSV. IRRI, 1985.

Designation	Plots (%) with \geq 50% fertility	Mean fertility ^a
Sitopas (check)	61.2	39.1 a
IR43301 (Sitopas//IR26702-52-3)	12.2	15.8 b
IR46641 (Sitopas//IR26702-52-3//IR8234-OT-9-2)	15.3	13.3 b
IR46630 (IR20/Sitopas//BR118-3B-17)	7.6	8.1 c
IR46733 (IR20/Sitopas//BR51-91-7)	4.2	2.8 d
IR46734 (IR20/Sitopas//New Sabarmati)	4.1	3.1 d
IR8234-OT-9-2 (check)	2.8	2.8 d
IR20 (check)	0.6	1.3 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Spacing was 30 cm between rows with 25 cm between plants, in a randomized complete block design with 2 replications. N at 100 kg/ha was applied in 2 splits. Spikelet fertility was used to evaluate level of tolerance for RSV.

Sitopas confirmed its tolerance.

IR20 and IR8234-OT-9-2 were intolerant. Crosses with IR43301 and IR46641 showed significant numbers of fertile plants (see table). They also had more plots with at least 50% fertility, showing that Sitopas was able to transmit its tolerance for RSV into some of its progeny. □

Sources of resistance to sheath rot (ShR)

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During 1985-86 thaladi season, 59 rice cultures were screened for resistance to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw.) Gams. under field conditions where disease pressure was very high. Nine cultures showed high resistance (see table). □

Resistance of rice cultures to ShR, 1985-86. Aduthurai, India.

Culture	Cross	Disease index ^a	Disease reaction ^a
Manoharasali	Donor	1	HR
RB2069-2-6-1	Swarnadhan/Andrewsali	1	HR
RP2071-18-1-1	Swarnadhan/NLR9674	1	HR
CR331-1-1-3	Jagannath/Mashuri	1	HR
IR9202-21-1	IR2053-521-1-1-K 116/KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9	1	HR
RP1057-35-1-1	KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9 RP 5-32/Pankaj	1	HR
VRS286-4-1	—	1	HR
VRS163-2-2-2-3	—	1	HR
ARC14529	—	1	HR
IET85 84	IET4141/CR98-7216	1	HR
TN1	—	7	HS
IET7575	Sona/Manoharsali	9	HS
IET4 141	RP29 1 /IR22	9	HS

^a Standard evaluation system for rice 1-9 scale. ^bHR = highly resistant, HS = highly susceptible.